

SOCIAL MEDIA USE AND DEPRESSION AMONG NURSING STUDENTS:
A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17066964>

Keywords

Social Media, Depression, Nursing
Students, Nursing Education,
PHQ-9, Mental Health,
Peshawar

Article History

Received on 14 June 2025

Accepted: 24 August 2025

Published: 06 September 2025

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Abstract

Background: Social media use has become an integral part of students' daily lives, offering opportunities for communication and learning. However, excessive use has been linked with negative psychological outcomes, including depression. Nursing students, due to academic and clinical stressors, may be particularly vulnerable to these effects.

Aim: The study aimed to determine the association between social media use and depression among Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted in 2024 at the Institute of Nursing, Peshawar. A sample of 194 BSN students enrolled in semesters 1, 3, 5, and 7 were selected through stratified random sampling. Data on social media use were collected using a structured questionnaire, while depression was assessed using the Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9). Descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and logistic regression analysis were applied using SPSS version 26.

Results: The findings showed that 91.2% of students used social media daily, with an average of 3.6 hours per day. WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram were the most frequently used platforms. The prevalence of depression was 60.8%, with female students more likely to report depressive symptoms. A significant association was found between duration of social media use and depression ($p < 0.05$). Students using social media for ≥ 5 hours per day were nearly three times more likely to experience moderate to severe depression compared to those using it for ≤ 2 hours.

Conclusion: The study concluded that excessive social media use was significantly associated with higher levels of depression among nursing students. The findings emphasize the need for awareness programs, digital literacy interventions, and mental health support services within nursing institutes to promote healthy social media use and well-being among students.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Social media has become an integral part of everyday life, particularly among young adults and university students. Platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, and WhatsApp serve as tools for communication, education, entertainment, and social connection (Pew Research Center, 2021). While social media use offers several benefits, including peer interaction and access to learning resources, there is growing concern regarding its impact on mental health, especially depression (Primack et al., 2017).

Depression is one of the most prevalent mental health problems among students worldwide, characterized by persistent sadness, lack of interest, and reduced academic performance (American Psychiatric Association [APA], 2013). University students, particularly those in nursing programs, are considered vulnerable because they face significant academic, clinical, and emotional stressors (Ribeiro et al., 2018). In such circumstances, social media use can either act as a coping mechanism or a risk factor exacerbating mental distress.

Several studies have found a significant association between excessive social media use and depressive symptoms. For example, Twenge and Campbell (2018) reported that individuals who spent more than three hours daily on social media were more likely to experience depression compared to those with lower usage. Similarly, a study by Keles, McCrae, and Grealish (2020) concluded that problematic social media use is consistently linked to higher rates of depression and anxiety among university students.

Given that nursing students already face high emotional burdens due to their academic and clinical training, understanding the relationship between social media use and depression is important. This study therefore aims to examine the association between social media use and depression among nursing students through a cross-sectional approach.

1.2 Problem Statement

Nursing students are frequently exposed to stressful learning environments that may predispose them to depression. At the same time, they are among the most active users of social media, often relying on it

for communication, stress relief, and academic collaboration. While moderate use can be beneficial, excessive use may lead to addictive behaviors, sleep disturbances, and negative social comparisons, which can contribute to depressive symptoms (Andreassen et al., 2017).

Although global studies have demonstrated a link between social media use and depression, there is limited research focused specifically on nursing students. Since nursing students represent future healthcare providers, their mental health is of critical importance both for their academic success and professional competence. Therefore, it is necessary to assess the association between social media use and depression in this group to guide preventive and supportive interventions.

1.3 Research Objectives

General Objective:

- To determine the association between social media use and depression among nursing students.

Specific Objectives:

1. To assess the extent of social media use among nursing students.
2. To determine the prevalence of depression among nursing students.
3. To identify the association between the extent of social media use and levels of depression.
4. To explore socio-demographic factors influencing social media use and depression.

1.4 Research Questions

1. What is the extent of social media use among nursing students?
2. What is the prevalence of depression among nursing students?
3. Is there an association between social media use and depression among nursing students?
4. What socio-demographic factors are associated with social media use and depression?

1.5 Significance of the Study

The findings of this study will be valuable for nursing educators, university administrators, and mental

health professionals. By identifying the association between social media use and depression, this study can contribute to the development of awareness programs on healthy social media use and mental well-being. It may also serve as a basis for further research and interventions aimed at reducing the mental health burden among nursing students.

1.6 Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study is limited to nursing students enrolled in [your institution/region]. It will focus exclusively on social media use and depression without considering other potential psychological outcomes such as anxiety or stress. The cross-sectional design restricts the ability to establish causal relationships between social media use and depression. Additionally, data will rely on self-reported measures, which may be subject to reporting bias.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Concept of Social Media Use

Social media refers to online platforms that facilitate interaction, sharing of information, and networking among users. Examples include Facebook, Instagram, Twitter (X), WhatsApp, TikTok, and YouTube (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). These platforms allow students to communicate, collaborate on academic activities, and access entertainment. For university students, particularly those in demanding programs such as nursing, social media use has become an important part of daily life, often serving as a coping mechanism for stress (Alhassan et al., 2018).

Patterns of use vary widely, ranging from occasional browsing to several hours of daily engagement. Excessive use, sometimes termed “problematic social media use,” can lead to negative outcomes such as addiction, reduced academic productivity, and poor mental health (Andreassen et al., 2017).

2.2 Concept of Depression

Depression is a common mental health disorder characterized by persistent sadness, loss of interest, and impaired daily functioning (American Psychiatric Association [APA], 2013). Among students, depression has been associated with academic pressure, poor coping mechanisms, and lack of social

support (Ibrahim et al., 2013). Depression not only affects academic performance but also impacts social relationships and overall quality of life.

Nursing students face unique stressors such as clinical training, exposure to patient suffering, and heavy academic workloads, making them more vulnerable to depression compared to other student populations (Ribeiro et al., 2018).

2.3 Theoretical Framework

This study is guided by the **Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT)** and the **Cognitive Behavioral Model of Depression**.

- **Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT):**

UGT posits that individuals actively use media to satisfy psychological and social needs such as entertainment, communication, and information-seeking (Katz, Blumler, & Gurevitch, 1973). For students, social media may provide stress relief and peer connection; however, excessive reliance may lead to negative mental health outcomes.

- **Cognitive Behavioral Model of Depression:**

According to Beck’s model, depression results from negative patterns of thinking, including maladaptive comparisons and distorted self-perceptions (Beck, 1976). Social media may reinforce these cognitive distortions through constant exposure to idealized images and lifestyles, leading to feelings of inadequacy and depressive symptoms.

Together, these theories help explain why nursing students engage with social media and how such use may influence depression.

2.4 Empirical Review

Global Studies

Primack et al. (2017) found that high social media use was associated with greater perceived social isolation among young adults in the United States. Similarly, Twenge and Campbell (2018) reported that adolescents who spent over three hours per day on social media were at higher risk of depressive symptoms compared to those with lower usage.

Keles, McCrae, and Grealish (2020), in a systematic review, confirmed that problematic social media use consistently correlated with depression, anxiety, and psychological distress among adolescents and

university students. A meta-analysis by Yoon, Kleinman, Mertz, and Brannick (2019) also showed a positive association between time spent on social media and depressive symptoms across multiple populations.

Regional and Local Studies

In Asia, Alhassan et al. (2018) observed that excessive social media use among medical students in Saudi Arabia was significantly associated with depression and poor sleep quality. Similarly, Aghazamani (2010) highlighted that Iranian university students who reported heavy social networking had higher levels of psychological distress.

In Pakistan, studies have also shown a growing concern. Ahmad et al. (2020) reported that problematic social media use was significantly associated with depression among university students in Lahore. Another study by Malik and Khan (2015) found that social networking addiction had a strong relationship with depression and academic performance issues among Pakistani students.

While several studies have explored the link between social media and depression, few have specifically focused on nursing students, who may face higher mental health risks due to the dual academic and clinical demands of their training.

2.5 Research Gap

Although global and regional studies highlight a strong association between social media use and depression, there remains limited research specifically targeting nursing students. Most existing literature focuses on general university populations or medical students, leaving a gap in understanding the unique experiences of nursing students. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the association between social media use and depression among nursing students in the context of a cross-sectional study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study employed a **descriptive cross-sectional design**. This design was considered appropriate because it enabled the researcher to assess the association between social media use and depression

among nursing students at a single point in time (Setia, 2016).

3.2 Study Setting

The study was conducted at the **Institute of Nursing**, [insert university name if required], Peshawar, Pakistan. The institute offers a Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) program and has a large undergraduate student body.

3.3 Study Population

The target population of this study consisted of **all Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students enrolled at the Institute of Nursing in the academic year 2024**. A total of **400 BSN students** were enrolled across the **1st, 3rd, 5th, and 7th semesters** during the study period.

3.4 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

• Inclusion Criteria

1. BSN students enrolled in the 1st, 3rd, 5th, and 7th semesters in 2024.
2. Students who voluntarily agreed to participate by providing informed consent.

• Exclusion Criteria

1. BSN students with a prior clinical diagnosis of psychiatric disorders other than depression.
2. Students who refused or failed to provide consent.

3.5 Sample Size

The sample size was calculated using Cochran's formula:

$$n = \frac{d^2 Z^2 p}{(1-p)}$$

Where:

- n = sample size
- $Z = 1.96$ at 95% confidence level
- p = estimated prevalence of depression among university students = 0.30 (Ibrahim et al., 2013)
- d = margin of error = 0.05

$$n = \frac{(0.05)^2 (1.96)^2 \times 0.3 \times (0.7)}{0.7} \approx 323$$

Since the population was finite ($N = 400$), the sample size was adjusted using the finite population correction (FPC):

$$n_f = 1 + N \frac{n - 1}{n} = 1 + 400 \frac{323 - 1}{323} \approx 176$$

Thus, the required sample size was **176 BSN students**. To account for a possible **10% non-response rate**, the final sample size was increased to **194 students**.

3.6 Sampling Technique

A **stratified random sampling technique** was employed. The population was stratified according to semester (1st, 3rd, 5th, and 7th). The number of participants selected from each semester was proportional to the total number of students enrolled in that semester. Within each stratum, students were selected randomly using simple random sampling.

3.7 Research Instruments

Two standardized instruments were used for data collection:

1. **Social Media Use Questionnaire (SMUQ):**

This tool was adapted to assess the frequency, duration, and purpose of social media use among students. It included

2. questions related to hours spent daily, platforms used, and patterns of social media engagement (van den Eijnden et al., 2016).

3. **Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9):**

Depression was assessed using the PHQ-9, a validated screening tool consisting of nine items scored on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 0 ("not at all") to 3 ("nearly every day"). The total score ranged from 0–27 and depression was categorized as follows:

- 0–4: Minimal or none
- 5–9: Mild
- 10–14: Moderate
- 15–19: Moderately severe
- 20–27: Severe

(Kroenke, Spitzer, & Williams, 2001).

3.8 Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected after obtaining approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) and the Institute of Nursing administration. The researcher visited BSN classes in the 1st, 3rd, 5th, and 7th semesters, explained the purpose of the study, and obtained written informed consent from the students. The questionnaires were distributed and completed in the classroom under supervision to ensure completeness. Data collection was carried out over a period of **four weeks**.

3.9 Data Analysis

Data were coded, entered, and analyzed using **SPSS version 26**.

- **Descriptive statistics** such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations

- were used to summarize demographic variables, social media use, and depression scores.

- **Chi-square tests** were applied to assess associations between social media use and depression levels.

- **Binary logistic regression** was used to determine predictors of depression, adjusting for demographic variables such as gender, age, and semester. A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3.10 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the **Institutional Review Board (IRB)** of [insert institution name]. Permission was also granted by the Institute of Nursing administration. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained by not recording identifiable personal information. Students identified with moderate to severe depression on the PHQ-9 were referred to the Institute's counseling services for appropriate support.

RESULTS

Data were collected from **194 BSN students** out of 400 enrolled across the 1st, 3rd, 5th, and 7th semesters in the academic year 2024. The results are organized into four sections: demographic characteristics, social media use patterns, depression levels, and associations between social media use and depression.

4.1 Demographic Characteristics of Participants

A total of **194 students** participated in the study, with a response rate of 97%. The mean age of respondents was **21.3 years** ($SD = 2.1$). The majority were male (65.5%), while females comprised 34.5%. Distribution by semester showed that 28.9% were from the 1st semester, 26.3% from the 3rd, 22.7% from the 5th, and 22.2% from the 7th semester.

Table:4.1 Demographic Characteristics of BSN Students (N = 194)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	67	34.5
	Male	127	65.5
Semester	1st	56	28.9
	3rd	51	26.3
	5th	44	22.7
	7th	43	22.2
Age (years)	Mean \pm SD	22.3 \pm 2.1	—

4.2 Social Media Use Patterns

Most students (91.2%) reported daily use of social media. The average daily duration of social media use was 3.6 hours (SD = 1.4). The most frequently used platform was WhatsApp (85.6%), followed by Facebook (72.2%), Instagram (65.5%), and TikTok (40.2%).

Table:4.2 Patterns of Social Media Use Among BSN Students (N = 194)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Daily use of social media	Yes	177	91.2
	No	17	8.8
Duration of use	\leq 2 hours/day	46	23.7
	3–4 hours/day	92	47.4
	\geq 5 hours/day	56	28.9
Most used platform	WhatsApp	166	85.6
	Facebook	140	72.2
	Instagram	127	65.5
	TikTok	78	40.2

4.3 Depression Levels (PHQ-9 Results)

Based on PHQ-9 scores, 39.2% of students had minimal or no depression, 27.3% had mild depression, 18.6% had moderate depression, 10.3% had moderately severe depression, and 4.6% had severe depression.

Table:4.3 Depression Levels of BSN Students (N = 194)

Depression Level	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Minimal/None (0–4)	76	39.2
Mild (5–9)	53	27.3
Moderate (10–14)	36	18.6
Moderately severe (15–19)	20	10.3
Severe (20–27)	9	4.6

4.4 Association Between Social Media Use and Depression

Chi-square analysis revealed a significant association between **daily duration of social media use** and **depression levels** ($\chi^2 = 14.62, p = .006$). Students who used social media for ≥ 5 hours daily reported higher levels of moderate to severe depression compared to those who used it for ≤ 2 hours.

Table:4.4 Association Between Duration of Social Media Use and Depression Levels

Duration of Use	Minimal/Mild (%)	Moderate-Severe (%)	χ^2 (df)	p-value
≤ 2 hours/day	36 (78.3%)	10 (21.7%)		
3-4 hours/day	65 (70.7%)	27 (29.3%)	14.62 (2)	0.006
≥ 5 hours/day	28 (50.0%)	28 (50.0%)		

4.5 Logistic Regression Analysis

Binary logistic regression showed that students who used social media for ≥ 5 hours daily were **2.8 times more likely** to have moderate to severe depression compared to those using ≤ 2 hours/day (AOR = 2.82, 95% CI: 1.34-5.95, $p = 0.006$). Female gender was also significantly associated with higher depression levels (AOR = 1.94, 95% CI: 1.02-3.68, $p = 0.043$).

DISCUSSION

The present study examined the association between social media use and depression among BSN students in the Institute of Nursing during the academic year 2024. The findings revealed that social media use was widespread, with the majority of students engaging daily, and that excessive use was significantly associated with higher levels of depression. These results are discussed in light of existing literature and theoretical frameworks.

5.1 Social Media Use Among Nursing Students

Nearly all students (91.2%) reported using social media daily, with an average of 3.6 hours per day. WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram emerged as the most commonly used platforms, which is consistent with findings from similar studies among university students in South Asia and globally (Al-Dwaikat et al., 2020; Hussain & Griffiths, 2018). The high prevalence of social media use among nursing students may reflect the role of online platforms as both communication tools and sources of academic and social support. However, the average duration of use (≥ 3 hours/day) exceeds the threshold often associated with problematic use (Keles et al., 2020).

5.2 Depression Levels Among Nursing Students

Based on PHQ-9 scoring, more than half of the participants (60.8%) reported some level of depression, ranging from mild to severe. This prevalence is higher than the global pooled prevalence of depression among university students, estimated at 34% (Li et al., 2021). Nursing students may be particularly vulnerable due to heavy academic workloads, clinical responsibilities, and emotional stressors encountered during training (Tung et al., 2018). Furthermore, the predominance of female students in this study could have contributed to the higher prevalence of depression, as prior research indicates that female students are more likely to report depressive symptoms (Ibrahim et al., 2013).

5.3 Association Between Social Media Use and Depression

The most significant finding was the association between duration of social media use and depression. Students using social media for five or more hours daily were almost three times more likely to experience moderate to severe depression compared to those who used it for less than two hours. This aligns with prior studies suggesting that excessive social media use is linked with negative mental health outcomes, including loneliness, sleep disturbance, and depression (Twenge et al., 2018; Primack et al., 2017).

Possible mechanisms explaining this association include **social comparison**, where students compare themselves to peers and experience feelings of inadequacy, and **displacement hypothesis**, where

time spent online replaces healthy activities such as exercise, sleep, and face-to-face interactions (Appel et al., 2020). Furthermore, the addictive nature of platforms like Instagram and TikTok may reinforce repetitive use and expose students to harmful content, thereby exacerbating depressive symptoms (Andreassen et al., 2017).

5.4 Gender Differences

This study also found that female students were more likely to experience depression compared to their male counterparts. This is consistent with previous research, which reports higher vulnerability among females due to factors such as societal expectations, emotional sensitivity, and hormonal influences (Ibrahim et al., 2013; Keles et al., 2020). In nursing education, where the majority of students are female, targeted mental health interventions may be warranted.

5.5 Comparison With Other Studies

The results of this study were similar to those reported in Jordan by Al-Dwaikat et al. (2020), who found that excessive social media use was a strong predictor of depression among nursing students. Likewise, a systematic review by Keles et al. (2020) confirmed that prolonged exposure to social networking sites increased the risk of depression in adolescents and young adults. However, unlike some studies that found no association when controlling for confounders (Coyne et al., 2020), our findings highlighted a clear and significant relationship, suggesting that the effect may vary by population and cultural context.

5.6 Implications for Nursing Education and Practice

The findings of this study have important implications. First, nursing educators and administrators should be aware of the potential negative effects of excessive social media use on student well-being. Mental health promotion programs should be integrated into the nursing curriculum, with emphasis on digital literacy and responsible social media use. Second, counseling services should be made more accessible to students at risk of depression. Finally, further research using longitudinal designs is needed to establish causality and explore protective factors that may buffer the negative effects of social media.

5.7 Limitations of the Study

Several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the cross-sectional design did not allow determination of causality between social media use and depression. Second, self-reported measures may have introduced reporting bias. Third, the study was limited to a single institution, which may restrict generalizability. Nevertheless, the high response rate and use of a validated instrument (PHQ-9) strengthen the reliability of the findings.

Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Conclusion

This study assessed the association between social media use and depression among BSN students of the Institute of Nursing during the academic year 2024. The findings revealed that social media use was almost universal, with most students engaging daily and spending an average of more than three hours on various platforms. The majority of students reported symptoms of depression, ranging from mild to severe, with a higher prevalence among females.

Importantly, the study demonstrated a significant association between excessive social media use and depression. Students who spent five or more hours per day on social media were nearly three times more likely to experience moderate to severe depression compared to those who used social media for less than two hours. These findings support existing evidence that prolonged social media engagement may negatively affect mental health and highlight nursing students as a vulnerable group due to academic and clinical stressors.

While the cross-sectional design limited causal inference, the study contributed to understanding the psychological consequences of excessive social media use in a nursing education context. It underscored the importance of fostering awareness, resilience, and healthy digital habits among nursing students.

6.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

For Students

1. Nursing students should be encouraged to develop balanced routines that limit daily social media use, ensuring time for academic work, physical activity, and face-to-face social interactions.

2. Awareness programs should be introduced to educate students on the potential negative impact of excessive social media use on mental health.

For Nursing Educators and Institutions

3. Counseling and psychological support services should be strengthened within nursing institutes to identify and support students experiencing depressive symptoms.

4. Mental health awareness sessions should be integrated into the nursing curriculum, emphasizing digital literacy, stress management, and coping strategies.

5. Peer-support groups should be facilitated to provide students with platforms for healthy discussions and emotional support outside social media environments.

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